

1. The need for this work comes from the fact that traditional solar sizing techniques are not reliable for sizing panels for continuous loads, such as automatic weather stations. This is because of seasonal variations of solar irradiance and short-term solar irradiance variations (due to cloudy days and intermittent sunshine). There is experimental data to support this. Fig. 1 below shows that the battery state of charge keeps falling even with a panel 4 times the size calculated from the traditional equation using hours of sunshine, load consumption and total consumption hours. The indication is that the solar panel is not generating sufficient energy to sustain the load. The research question is then "How do we establish the required solar panel size to ensure the battery never goes below a given state of charge in a given time period?" One quick and fast technique is, of course, to oversize the panel by a large margin. There are 2 challenges with this:
 - i. Cost implications – especially when several stations are going to be deployed
 - ii. Larger panels will have some domestic value and have been known to attract vandals/thieves in developing countries such as Uganda, Tanzania and Brazil.

Figure 1

2. Solar panel sizing is mainly an issue for the gateway, which consumes the largest amount of power in a Wireless Sensor Network (WSN). In the 1st objective, we suggested guidelines for designing very low power gateways (to maximize battery life and prevent short-term failure due to insufficient power). We also made a reference implementation of such a gateway. Now I am obtaining data from actual field deployments.
3. The mode of operation of the gateway typically as follows.
 - a. The uplink is in sleep mode by default (consuming about 2.6mA). It is an Electron 3G with a microcontroller to which an SD card has been attached
 - b. The sink node which receives reports of weather data from the transmitter node is connected to the uplink and is always on (consuming about 12mA)
 - c. When a given number of reports have been accumulated, the uplink device turns on the 3G module and connects to the server, uploading all the data and then resuming the sleep state. The current consumed in this state is about 280-380mA. The time to upload depends on the data available on the SD card.
 - d. The battery is a Li-ion battery operating between 3.3-4.2V. It's state of charge is measured by the MAX17043 Fuel Gauge IC on the electron.
4. The operation stated in (3) makes using analytical techniques quite complicated. Over and above the dynamic solar irradiance variation, there is some variation in the stated currents since the battery voltage is not constant (due to charge-discharge), upload time (which may be affected by network quality) and even temperature of the battery.

5. Hence, we propose a black-box approach in which we establish the behavior of the system by using actual experimental data collected in an outdoor uncontrolled experiment over a long period of time. The state of charge of the battery is an accurate representation of the net power output from the solar panel, less the gateway consumption. It indicates how much of the incident solar radiation has been stored as electrochemical energy for later use. By looking, therefore, at the solar radiation as the input and battery SOC as the output, we can model the behavior of the whole gateway as a function, and use this function to predict battery states given a known solar irradiance profile, which can easily be obtained from the UNMA (and other national meteorological departments)
6. Models of physical systems are either linear or non-linear. We propose a linear model as a start. This is because the relationship between solar irradiance and power output of solar panels is in fact linear .Fig. 2 below shows this.

Figure 2

Figure from A. E. Githas (2012), *Studying the effect of spectral variations intensity of the incident solar radiation on the Si solar cells performance*, NRIAG Journal of Astronomy and Geophysics, vol.1, issue 2, pp165-171
 More clearly, from Figure 2, we can derive Fig. 3 that shows how power output and solar irradiance vary on different axes.

Figure 3

Further, we have experimental observations that indicate that the battery state of charge and solar radiation also follow an approximately similar pattern as shown below in Fig. 4

Figure 4

If we split the graph into the charging phase (up to approx. 2pm) and the discharging phase, we obtain the scatter graphs shown below in Figs 5 and 6 with their trend lines and correlation co-efficient. The graph on the left shows the variation of the two parameters during charge and that on the right during discharge. The correlation coefficients show a strong linear relationship.

Figure 5

Figure 6

It is therefore justified to propose a linear model relationship between solar irradiance and battery state of charge. Since we have justified that a linear model will be an accurate representation, we can now focus on linear system identification (model development). In control theory, most popular technique is transfer function estimation. In theory, the system can be represented as the figure below where \mathbf{x} is the input, \mathbf{h} is the transfer function and \mathbf{y} is the output:

In deterministic physical systems, such as a mass on a spring or an electric circuit, h can be derived using analytical techniques such as Laplace or Z transforms and is the ratio of the output to the input in the frequency domain. Since from the experimental data we have the input **solar insolation** and the output **battery state of charge**, we can estimate $H(z)$.

7. Using a 1W and 2W solar panels, we collected battery SOC data between Feb 15 and June 14 and obtained solar irradiance data from UNMA for Makerere university weather station where the gateway is deployed. Using the MATLAB system identification app, we estimated the transfer function using the data collected with the 2W solar panel. The deployment with the 2W solar panel was the preferred one because it never got to 0% SOC thus allowing the experiment to continue uninterrupted.
8. By iteratively increasing the number of poles and zeros, the system could be modelled with a ~80% goodness of fit for the observed and predicted data. We used 4 poles and 3 zeros (using a higher number did not improve accuracy of fit very much). We were able to use the generated transfer function to compare the predicted SOC with the actual observed SOC. The graphs below shows the results.

Figure 7

In Figure 7, we use the data of June 1-12 to develop the system model and then part of the same data (June 4-12) to validate it. We get a strong positive correlation of 0.915 and a small root mean prediction error of 5.8 meaning that, on average, the model underestimates or overestimates the battery SOC by 5.8 units.

In figure 8 below, we used a dataset from Feb 15-28 to develop the model and validated it against the observed data from March 14 – 21. We get a smaller but still strong positive correlation and a RMSE of 9

Figure 8

units.

9. For prediction far into the future, a representative solar irradiance profile can be generated from historic data for, say, 3 years and then used in prediction. The output below shows the backwards-predicted battery SOC from January to June 2018. It shows that if the 2W solar panel had been deployed in January, the minimum state of charge would have been registered as 27% on April 26th. Even if in practical terms we expect this to vary, since the daily patterns are different year-on-year, an average (ensemble/representative) solar insolation profile would give very confident minimum SOC values that can be used for sizing.

We can simulate what this output would have been, using a panel of any wattage, buy simply multiplying the input solar insolation by an appropriate constant since we have already shown the solar irradiance and power output to have a very linear relationship.

10. The other technique to be considered is using discrete calculus. We shall use a computer program to calculate the actual Wh of electrical energy stored by looking at the voltage and SOC plots over several weeks in both the 1W and 2W deployments and use this to derive the net energy delivered in a unit time by a unit solar panel wattage. I am still assessing if there is need to look into non-linear techniques, given the good correlations from linear techniques and the time I have left.